

APPENDIX

Shaded fraction and backtracking in single-axis trackers on rolling terrain

Adam R. Jensen

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Appendix – Shaded fraction and backtracking in single-axis trackers on rolling terrain

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By
Adam R. Jensen

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0 Update - 2025-11-05

This appendix was updated on 2025-11-05 by adding an extra decimal to the Z_R values in Table 3. Specifically, the Z_R values which were previously listed as 0.1 should in fact be 0.12 for the test cases to match. The same mistake occurs in the journal article (doi: 10.1063/5.0202220).

1 Overview

This document is an appendix to the journal paper "Shaded fraction and backtracking in single-axis trackers on rolling terrain" authored by Kevin S. Anderson and Adam R. Jensen. The paper was submitted to the Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy in January 2024.

In addition to this document, the appendix consists of several supplementary files which are made available at the open research data repository Zenodo (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10513988). An overview of the supplementary files is provided in Table 1 and described in the following sections.

Description	Filename
bifacial_radiance output	bifacial_radiance_shaded_fraction_fixed_tilt.csv bifacial_radiance_shaded_fraction_single_axis.csv
Python functions	variable_terrain_shaded_fraction.py variable_terrain_backtracking.py
Test cases	cases_shaded_fraction.csv cases_bactracking.csv
Python tests	test_variable_terrain_shaded_fraction.py test_variable_terrain_backtracking.py

Table 1: Overview of supplementary files.

2 bifacial_radiance output

The shaded fractions calculated using `bifacial_radiance` for the two validation cases in the paper (Section III B) are provided as CSV files. These files allow future studies to compare alternative software or methods to our simulation results. The necessary details to replicate the simulations are provided in the paper.

The `bifacial_radiance` shaded fraction CSV files each contains three columns. The first column is the simulation timestamp. The last two columns correspond to the lower (min) and upper (max) bounds of the estimated shaded fraction.

3 Python functions

To make adoption of the variable terrain shaded fraction method as easy as possible, we provide a simple implementation in the Python programming language. The function `shaded_fraction` is contained within the `variable_terrain_shaded_fraction.py` file and calculates the shaded fraction given inputs of tracker angles and geometry as well as the projected solar zenith angle. Similarly, the `variable_terrain_backtracking.py` file contains the function `backtracking_theta_1` for calculating the backtracking angle of a front tracker (θ_1) given the maximum acceptable shading fraction and geometric parameters of the rear tracker. All functions are documented using in-code documentation following the `numpydoc` style and rely only on standard Python libraries.

4 Test cases

To facilitate implementation of the shading calculation and backtracking method, we provide a set of test cases with expected calculation results. Test cases for the shaded fraction calculation are listed in Table 2 and visualized in Figure 1. Test cases for the backtracking calculation are listed in Table 3 and visualized in Figure 2. The visualizations of the test cases can be found in Section 6. Note, for the backtracking test cases, it is assumed that the collectors are positioned parallel to the sun line if shading cannot be avoided. For a description of the variables within the file, the reader is referred to the journal article or the Python code documentation.

Case	x_L	z_L	θ_L	x_R	z_R	θ_R	z_0	ℓ	θ_s	f_s^*
1	1	0.2	50	0	0.0	25	0.00	0.5	80	1.000000
2	1	0.1	50	0	0.0	25	0.05	0.5	80	0.937191
3	1	0.0	50	0	0.1	25	0.00	0.5	80	0.306050
4	1	0.0	50	0	0.2	25	0.00	0.5	80	0.000000
5	1	0.2	-25	0	0.0	-50	0.00	0.5	-80	0.000000
6	1	0.1	-25	0	0.0	-50	0.00	0.5	-80	0.306050
7	1	0.0	-25	0	0.1	-50	0.10	0.5	-80	0.881549
8	1	0.0	-25	0	0.2	-50	0.00	0.5	-80	1.000000
9	1	0.2	5	0	0.0	25	0.05	0.5	80	0.832499
10	1	0.2	-25	0	0.0	25	0.05	0.5	80	0.832499
11	1	0.2	5	0	0.0	-45	0.05	0.5	80	0.832499
12	1	0.2	-25	0	0.0	-45	0.05	0.5	80	0.832499
13	1	0.0	-25	0	0.2	25	0.05	0.5	-80	0.832499
14	1	0.0	-25	0	0.2	-5	0.05	0.5	-80	0.832499
15	1	0.0	45	0	0.2	25	0.05	0.5	-80	0.832499
16	1	0.0	45	0	0.2	-5	0.05	0.5	-80	0.832499

Table 2: Test cases for the shaded fraction calculation.

Case	x_L	z_L	x_R	z_R	z_0	ℓ	θ_s	f_s^*	θ_2	θ_1
1	1	0.1	0	0.0	0.025	0.5	80	0.00	30	-10.000000
2	1	0.0	0	0.0	0.025	0.5	80	0.00	30	-8.369714
3	1	0.0	0	0.12	0.025	0.5	80	0.00	30	21.025781
4	1	0.0	0	0.2	0.025	0.5	80	0.00	30	50.031945
5	1	0.1	0	0.0	0.025	0.5	80	0.25	30	-10.000000
6	1	0.0	0	0.0	0.025	0.5	80	0.25	30	10.877359
7	1	0.0	0	0.12	0.025	0.5	80	0.25	30	50.915129
8	1	0.0	0	0.2	0.025	0.5	80	0.25	30	80.000000
9	1	0.1	0	0.0	0.025	0.5	80	0.50	30	6.338550
10	1	0.0	0	0.0	0.025	0.5	80	0.50	30	34.407694
11	1	0.0	0	0.12	0.025	0.5	80	0.50	30	80.000000
12	1	0.0	0	0.2	0.025	0.5	80	0.50	30	80.000000
13	1	0.1	0	0.0	0.025	0.5	-80	0.00	-30	-15.604247
14	1	0.0	0	0.0	0.025	0.5	-80	0.00	-30	8.369714
15	1	0.0	0	0.12	0.025	0.5	-80	0.00	-30	10.000000
16	1	0.0	0	0.2	0.025	0.5	-80	0.00	-30	10.000000
17	1	0.1	0	0.0	0.025	0.5	-80	0.25	-30	-41.380899
18	1	0.0	0	0.0	0.025	0.5	-80	0.25	-30	-10.877359
19	1	0.0	0	0.12	0.025	0.5	-80	0.25	-30	10.000000
20	1	0.0	0	0.2	0.025	0.5	-80	0.25	-30	10.000000
21	1	0.1	0	0.0	0.025	0.5	-80	0.50	-30	-80.000000
22	1	0.0	0	0.0	0.025	0.5	-80	0.50	-30	-34.407694
23	1	0.0	0	0.12	0.025	0.5	-80	0.50	-30	-1.567397
24	1	0.0	0	0.2	0.025	0.5	-80	0.50	-30	10.000000

Table 3: Test cases for the backtracking calculation.

5 Python tests

Comparison of the outputs from the provided Python functions described in Section 3 are provided in the two test files (`test_variable_terrain_shaded_fraction.py` and `test_variable_terrain_backtracking.py`). Executing the two test files requires that all of the supplemental files be located in the working directory.

6 Visualization of test cases

This section contains the illustration of the test cases in Section 4.

Figure 1: Visualization of the shaded fraction test cases.

Figure 2: Visualization of the backtracking test cases.